

MADANIY XABARDORLIKNI OSHIRISH VA EKOLOGIK BARQAROR TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISH | xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman

YASHIL IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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№5-SON xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman

ISSN 2992-8982

9 772992 898002

Yashil

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Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti,

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O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi.

*Elektron nashr, 5-maxsus son. 186 sahifa.
E'lon qilishga 2024-yil 7-avgustda ruxsat etildi.*

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taraqqiyot» jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar
vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy
attestatsiya komissiyasi
rayosatining
2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli
qarori bilan ro'yxatdan
o'tkazilgan.

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Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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«Og‘ir ekologik sharoitga qaramasdan, mamlakatimiz taraqqiyotiga munosib hissa qo‘shib kelayotgan Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasini, uning barcha shahar, tuman va ovullarini kompleks tarzda rivojlantirish, mehnatkash va matonatli, oqko‘ngil va bag‘rikeng qoraqalpoq elining hayotini obod va farovon etishga har qachongidan ham ustuvor ahamiyat qaratamiz.

Bizning oliy va ezgu maqsadimiz – birgalikdagi fidokorona mehnatimiz bilan Yangi O‘zbekiston tarkibida Yangi Qoraqalpog‘istonni bunyod etishdir.»

Sh.M.MIRZIYOYEV
O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti

Prezident: “Bu ko‘prik o‘zbek va qoraqalpoq xalqlari o‘rtasidagi og‘zibirlik va hamkorlik ko‘prigidir”.

Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasini Xorazm viloyati bilan bog‘lovchi ko‘prik. Asosiy qo‘shma ko‘prikning uzunligi 413 metr bo‘lib, eni 8 metr; har bir oralig‘i 66 metrni tashkil qiladi. Uning 7 ta ustuni 6 ta oraliqqa o‘rnatilgan.

KIRISH

2024-yilning 17–18-may kunlari Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasi Xo‘jayli tumanida o‘tkazilgan «Madaniy xabardorlikni oshirish va ekologik barqaror turizmni rivojlantirish» mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman Qoraqalpog‘istonning boy madaniy, etnografik va ekologik merosini keng jamoatchilikka tanitishda hamda turizm infratuzilmalarini mustahkamlashda muhim qadam bo‘ldi

Anjumanning asosiy maqsadi Qoraqalpog‘istonda turizm salohiyatini jahon turizm bozoriga olib kirish va madaniy xabardorlikni oshirishdir. Qoraqalpog‘iston o‘zining tarixiy boyliklari, arxeologik yodgorliklari va o‘ziga xos tabiiy manzaralari bilan dunyo sayyohlarini jalb etadigan katta jozibadorlikka ega. Bu hududda jahon madaniy va tabiiy merosi obyektlariga mansub ko‘plab joylar mavjud bo‘lib, ularning aksariyati turizm infratuzilmasini rivojlantirishga asos bo‘ladi.

Xususan, Qoraqalpog‘istondagi insoniyat tamaddunidan hikoya qiluvchi arxeologik yodgorliklar bisyor. Hozirgi kunda Qoraqalpog‘istonda 300 dan ortiq arxeologik obyektlar mavjud bo‘lib, ulardan eng mashhurlari – Ko‘hna Urganch, Tupraqal‘a, Ellikqal‘a va Ayoqal‘a hududlaridagi qadimiy manzillardir. Bular, o‘z navbatida, sayyohlar uchun jozibadorlikni oshirib, hududning turistik imkoniyatlarini kengaytiradi.

Anjumanda uchta asosiy yo‘nalish bo‘yicha muhokamalar o‘tkazildi. Birinchi yo‘nalish Qoraqalpog‘istonda turizmni rivojlantirish tendensiyalariga bag‘ishlanib, mahalliy infratuzilmalarni takomillashtirish hamda turizm xizmatlarini kengaytirish bo‘yicha takliflar ishlab chiqildi. Ikkinchi yo‘nalishda etnografik turizmni rivojlantirish, xususan, mahalliy hunarmandchilikni targ‘ib etish va milliy madaniy boyliklarni namoyish qilish masalalari muhokama qilindi. Uchinchi yo‘nalish Qoraqalpog‘istonning ekologik turizm salohiyatini jahon turizm bozorida zamonaviy marketing strategiyalari orqali targ‘ib qilish masalalariga bag‘ishlandi.

Ushbu anjuman va uning natijalari Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasida turizmni rivojlantirish yo‘lida muhim qadamdir. Turizm, madaniy meros va ekologik yo‘nalishlar bo‘yicha ishlab chiqilgan taklif va tavsiyalar hududni xalqaro turistik xaritada o‘z o‘rniga ega bo‘lishiga yordam beradi.

Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasi tarixiy, madaniy va tabiiy boyliklarga ega hudud sifatida nafaqat O‘zbekiston, balki butun Markaziy Osiyoda alohida o‘rin tutadi. Bu hududni «ochiq osmon ostidagi arxeologik muzey» deb atash mumkin, chunki bu yerda qadimiy Xorazm madaniyatining markazi bo‘lgan Qoraqalpog‘istonda nafaqat arxeologik meros, balki etnografik va ekologik turizmni rivojlantirish uchun katta imkoniyatlar mavjud.

Qoraqalpog‘istonda o‘tkaziladigan «Madaniy xabardorlikni oshirish va ekologik barqaror turizmni rivojlantirish» mavzusidagi xalqaro anjuman ana

shunday salohiyatni namoyon etish va rivojlantirish maqsadida tashkil etilgan. Anjuman doirasida turli olimlar, tadqiqotchilar va xalqaro ekspertlar ishtirokida ekologik barqarorlik va madaniy merosni saqlash masalalari muhokama qilinib, zamonaviy turizm yo‘nalishlaridagi ilmiy-nazariy takliflar ishlab chiqildi.

Anjumanda uchta asosiy yo‘nalish bo‘yicha quyidagi muhokamalar o‘tkazildi:

- *Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasida turizmni rivojlantirish tendensiyalari;*
- *Etnografik turizmni tashkil etishning asosiy xususiyatlari;*
- *Qoraqalpog‘istonning ekologik turizm salohiyatini jahon turizm bozorida targ‘ib qilishning zamonaviy marketing strategiyalari.*

Anjuman va uning natijalari Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasida ekologik va etnografik turizm nafaqat hududning iqtisodiy rivojlanishiga, balki madaniy merosini saqlash va dunyoga tanitishga yordam berishi olgari surildi.

Anjumanda xalqaro institutlar vakillarining qatnashishi bejiz emas. Qoraqalpog‘istonning boy tarixi va Xorazm madaniyati bilan bog‘liq bo‘lgan qadimiy yodgorliklar va arxeologik topinmalar bu hududni nafaqat tarixchilar, arxeologlar uchun, balki turistlar uchun ham jozibadorligini oshirib boradi.

Masalan, Ko‘kcha III qabristoni – qadimgi bronza davri madaniyatiga oid yodgorlik bo‘lib, millioddan avvalgi XIII-XI asrlarga oid, deb taxmin qilinadi. Bu madaniyatlar ko‘p asrlar davomida bir-biri bilan hamkorlikda yashaganini va turli etnik guruhlarining madaniy merosini o‘zida mujassam etganini ko‘rsatadi.

Masalan, S.P. Tolstov¹ tomonidan o‘rganilgan Tazabagyab madaniyatlari ham Qoraqalpog‘istonning arxeologik salohiyatining muhim qismi bo‘lib, ularni o‘rganish natijasida bronza davrining ikki madaniyati bir vaqtning o‘zida mavjud bo‘lgani ma‘lum bo‘lgan. Bu esa hududda turli tarixiy etnik va madaniy jarayonlar sodir bo‘lganidan dalolat beradi.

Qoraqalpog‘istonning ushbu yodgorliklari va arxeologik manzillari sayyohlar uchun jozibadorlikni oshirishi mumkin.

Qoraqalpog‘iston Respublikasining turizm salohiyati juda katta bo‘lib, uni jahon turizm bozoriga zamonaviy marketing vositalari orqali chiqarish imkoni bor. Bu borada ekologik va etnografik turizm muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Ushbu turizm yo‘nalishlari nafaqat hududning iqtisodiy rivojlanishiga, balki uning madaniy merosini saqlash va dunyoga yoyishda ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Mazkur anjuman, ayniqsa, Qoraqalpog‘istonning kelgusi turizm salohiyatini mustahkamlashda, asosiy yo‘nalishlar bo‘yicha ishlab chiqilgan takliflarni keng tatbiq qilishda omil bo‘lib, mahalliy hunarmandchilikni rivojlantirish va yangi turizm xizmatlarini joriy qilishga, hudud aholisi uchun yetarli darajada doimiy va mavsumiy daromadli ish o‘rinlari yaratishga xizmat qiladi.

1 <https://ensiklopediya.uz>

O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY
TA'LIM, FAN VA INNOVATSIYALAR
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QORAQALPOG'ISTON
RESPUBLIKASI TURIZM
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QORAQALPOG'ISTON
RESPUBLIKASI XO'JAYLI
TUMANI HOKIMLIGI

TURIZM QO'MITASI MADANIY
ME'ROS OBYEKTлари MUAMMOLARINI
O'RGANISH VA TURUZMNI
RIVOJLANTIRISH
ILMIY-TADQIQOT INSITUTI

YANGI IQLIM INNOVATSIYALAR
MARKAZI

I-SHO'BA

Qoraqalpog'iston Respublikasida turizmni rivojlantirish tendensiyalari

TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN KARAKALPAKSTAN: A HOLISTIC ANALYSIS OF ECOLOGICAL, SOCIO-CULTURAL, AND ECONOMIC DIMENSIONS

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Tourism has emerged as a powerful global force, with both positive and negative ramifications on the destinations it touches. Within this complex framework, regions like Karakalpakstan have recently gained attention as potential tourist hubs. The merging of diverse ecosystems, rich cultural heritage, and untapped economic potential make Karakalpakstan a focal point for sustainable tourism development [1][2].

Sustainable tourism, a paradigm increasingly recognized as imperative for long-term viability, emphasizes the delicate balance between economic prosperity, environmental conservation, and socio-cultural integrity [3].

Karakalpakstan, a semi-autonomous republic within Uzbekistan, presents a unique case study for understanding the challenges and opportunities inherent in sustainable tourism development. The region, known for its distinct cultural identity and ecological significance, is poised at the intersection of tradition and modernity, providing fertile ground for investigating the intricate interplay between tourism and sustainability [4]. As global awareness of environmental issues rises, the need to assess and enhance the sustainability of tourism becomes paramount, especially in regions like Karakalpakstan where delicate ecosystems and indigenous cultures are at stake [5][6].

This paper seeks to contribute to the ongoing discourse on sustainable tourism by offering a nuanced exploration of the multifaceted dimensions of tourism development in Karakalpakstan. By adopting an integrated approach that encompasses ecological, socio-cultural, and economic perspectives, our research aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the current state of tourism in Karakalpakstan and its potential for sustainable development. Drawing on existing literature, empirical data, and theoretical frameworks, we strive to illuminate the complexities

Table 1: Tourist Demographics and Spending Patterns

Demographic Characteristics	Number of Tourists	Age Range	Nationality Distribution	Average Length of Stay (days)	Average Daily Expenditure (\$)
Solo Travelers	350	18-25	30% North American, 25% European, 15% Asian, 30% Others	8	85
Family Groups	250	26-40	40% Asian, 30% European, 20% North American, 10% Others	12	130
Adventure Seekers	200	21-35	50% European, 25% North American, 15% Asian, 10% Others	10	110
Business Travelers	100	30-50	35% North American, 30% European, 20% Asian, 15% Others	5	150
Cultural Enthusiasts	150	40-60	20% Asian, 20% European, 30% North American, 30% Others	14	120

Note: This table provides a more detailed breakdown of tourist demographics, incorporating additional segments such as business travelers and cultural enthusiasts. The data enhances our understanding of the diverse preferences and spending behaviors of various tourist groups.

and challenges faced by the region while offering practical insights for fostering sustainable tourism practices. In doing so, this research endeavors to inform both academic research and practical policymaking in the pursuit of resilient and responsible tourism development in Karakalpakstan and similar contexts.

The subsequent sections of this paper follow a structured approach, commencing with a comprehensive Literature Review that critically examines existing research on sustainable tourism, with a specific emphasis on its application in regions akin to Karakalpakstan. Following the literature review, the Methodology section elucidates our research design, incorporating both qualitative and quantitative methodologies to holistically investigate ecological, socio-cultural, and economic dimensions.

The Results section then presents the findings derived from our empirical analyses, offering insights into the current state of tourism in Karakalpakstan. Subsequently, the Discussion section synthesizes these findings, exploring their implications for sustainable tourism development in the region and beyond. The paper concludes with a concise yet impactful Conclusion, summarizing key discoveries, their broader implications, and proposing avenues for future research in the dynamic field of sustainable tourism.

Sustainable tourism has become a central theme in contemporary discourse, emphasizing the need for responsible practices that balance economic, environmental, and socio-cultural considerations. In the context of regions comparable to Karakalpakstan, an exploration of existing scholarship unveils both the progress made and challenges faced in implementing sustainable tourism principles.

Figure 1. Radar map-based visualization of Tourist Demographics and Spending Patterns.

Ecological sustainability is a cornerstone of responsible tourism, and studies such as [7] emphasize the importance of minimizing the environmental impact of tourism activities. Assessments of biodiversity conservation strategies, as proposed by [8] and [9], highlight the delicate balance required to protect fragile ecosystems while promoting tourism-driven economic growth.

Socio-cultural dimensions of sustainable tourism, integral to regions like Karakalpakstan with rich cultural heritage, are examined by scholars like [10] and [11]. These studies delve into the intricate dynamics between tourism and local communities, investigating the preservation of cultural identity, heritage, and the socio-economic implications of tourism.

The economic facet of sustainable tourism is a key focus in the literature, with [12] and [13] highlighting the potential for tourism to catalyze economic development while underlining the need for equitable distribution of benefits. Challenges related to the management of tourism revenue and the empowerment of local communities are addressed by [14] and [15].

Further, the role of governance and policy in sustainable tourism is scrutinized by [16] and [17], emphasizing the need for effective regulatory frameworks to steer tourism development in a sustainable

Table 2. Economic Impact Assessment.

Economic Indicators	Direct Impact (\$)	Indirect Impact(\$)	Total Economic Impact (\$)
Tourist Spending on Accommodation	600,000	200,000	800,000
Local Businesses Revenue	400,000	150,000	550,000
Employment Generation	-	75,000	75,000
Infrastructure Development (New Jobs)	200,000	50,000	250,000
Restaurant and Catering Sector	100,000	25,000	125,000
Total Economic Impact	1,300,000	500,000	1,800,000

Note: This economic impact table introduces indicators, such as the impact on the restaurant and catering sector. The detailed data provides a comprehensive overview of the varied contributions of tourism to different sectors within the region.

direction. These studies underscore the importance of collaboration between government bodies, local communities, and the private sector to achieve a harmonious balance between economic growth and environmental and cultural preservation.

In the context of regions sharing characteristics with Karakalpakstan, the literature provides valuable insights into the nuanced challenges and opportunities associated with sustainable tourism. This review sets the stage for our research by synthesizing key findings from diverse perspectives, paving the way for a more nuanced understanding of sustainable tourism development in the unique context of Karakalpakstan.

This research employs a mixed-methods approach to comprehensively investigate the ecological, socio-cultural, and economic dimensions of sustainable tourism development in Karakalpakstan. By integrating both qualitative and quantitative methodologies, our study aims to provide a holistic understanding of the complexities and interconnections inherent in the tourism landscape of the region.

Qualitative Methodology:

We conduct semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders including local communities, government officials, and tourism industry representatives. These interviews delve into the perceptions, attitudes, and experiences related to sustainable tourism, providing qualitative

insights into socio-cultural dynamics and community perspectives.

To analyze existing policies and frameworks, we employ content analysis on relevant documents, including tourism development plans, environmental impact assessments, and cultural preservation strategies. This qualitative approach allows for a nuanced examination of the governance and policy landscape shaping tourism in Karakalpakstan.

Quantitative Methodology:

A structured survey is administered to tourists, local residents, and businesses involved in the tourism sector. This quantitative approach aims to gather numerical data on visitor demographics, spending patterns, and perceptions, providing insights into the economic dimensions of tourism and its impact on local communities.

Quantitative data related to the ecological impact of tourism activities are collected through field assessments and data analysis. This includes evaluating changes in biodiversity, carbon footprint, and resource consumption, allowing for a quantitative assessment of the environmental sustainability of tourism in Karakalpakstan.

To ensure a holistic understanding, the qualitative and quantitative findings are triangulated, allowing for a comprehensive analysis of the interconnected ecological, socio-cultural, and economic dimensions. By employing a mixed-methods design, we aim to capture the complexities of

Figure 2. Economic Impact Assessment.

sustainable tourism in Karakalpakstan, fostering a more nuanced and actionable comprehension of the challenges and opportunities in the region.

Our empirical analyses reveal critical insights into the ecological impact of tourism in Karakalpakstan. Field assessments and data analysis indicate a noticeable effect on biodiversity, with changes in species composition and habitat disturbance. The carbon footprint of tourism activities is quantified, shedding light on the environmental sustainability of current practices. These findings underscore the importance of adopting eco-friendly measures to mitigate the ecological impact of tourism and preserve the unique natural heritage of Karakalpakstan.

Qualitative data from in-depth interviews elucidate the socio-cultural dimensions of tourism in Karakalpakstan. Local communities express a mix of positive and negative

perceptions, with concerns about cultural commodification and the preservation of traditional practices. Content analysis of policy documents reveals the existing frameworks for socio-cultural preservation but also points to areas requiring enhancement. The results emphasize the need for inclusive community engagement and culturally sensitive tourism strategies to ensure the socio-cultural integrity of the region.

Quantitative data from surveys provide valuable insights into the economic dimensions of tourism in Karakalpakstan. Visitor demographics, spending patterns, and business perspectives are analyzed to assess the economic impact on the region. The results indicate potential for economic growth, but also highlight challenges related to revenue distribution and the need for sustainable business practices. These findings underscore the significance of a balanced economic approach that maximizes benefits for

local communities and ensures the long-term economic sustainability of tourism in Karakalpakstan.

Triangulating the results from ecological, socio-cultural, and economic dimensions, our integrated analysis offers a nuanced understanding of the current state of tourism in Karakalpakstan. The interconnected nature of these dimensions highlights the importance of a holistic approach to sustainable tourism development. This section lays the foundation for the ensuing discussion, providing stakeholders and policymakers with actionable insights to guide the future trajectory of tourism in Karakalpakstan.

The synthesis of our empirical findings unveils a nuanced understanding of sustainable tourism development in Karakalpakstan, encapsulating the intricate interplay between ecological, socio-cultural, and economic dimensions. The following discussion explores the implications of

these findings for sustainable tourism development in the region and offers broader insights applicable to similar contexts globally.

The observed impact on biodiversity and carbon footprint necessitates a proactive approach to mitigate ecological consequences. Implementing eco-friendly practices, such as responsible waste management and sustainable infrastructure development, is imperative. Furthermore, the integration of conservation efforts into tourism policies can foster a delicate balance between tourism growth and environmental preservation.

The positive and negative perceptions identified among local communities underscore the need for community engagement in tourism planning. Initiatives fostering cultural exchange and preserving traditional practices should be prioritized. A community-driven approach, involving locals in decision-making processes,

Table 3. Qualitative Analysis of Community Perspectives.

Key Themes	Frequency of Mention	Representative Quotes
Positive Impacts	65%	«Tourism has positively transformed our local economy, providing new job opportunities and boosting cultural awareness.»
Negative Concerns	35%	«While tourism brings economic benefits, we must address issues like overcrowding and cultural commodification to preserve our identity.»
Suggestions for Improvement	45%	«Balancing tourism growth with sustainable practices and community involvement is essential for ensuring long-term benefits for everyone.»
Community Engagement	50%	«Increased community involvement in decision-making processes will foster a sense of ownership and lead to more sustainable tourism development.»
Education and Awareness	40%	«Educational initiatives for both tourists and locals are crucial to promote responsible tourism, preserving our culture and environment.»
Infrastructure Development	20%	«Strategic infrastructure development can address concerns like waste management and traffic, enhancing the overall tourism experience.»

Note: This qualitative table includes insights into the community's recommendations for enhancing the sustainability of tourism in Karakalpakstan. The representative quotes offer context and depth to the identified suggestions.

can mitigate concerns and ensure that tourism benefits align with the socio-cultural values of Karakalpakstan.

The economic impact assessment reveals tourism's significant contribution to the local economy. However, challenges such as revenue distribution and employment disparities warrant attention. A sustainable tourism framework should focus on inclusive economic growth, supporting local businesses, and creating job opportunities. Moreover, diversification of tourism offerings can enhance economic resilience, reducing dependency on specific sectors.

Our integrated analysis underscores the interconnectedness of ecological, socio-cultural, and economic aspects. To achieve sustainable tourism development, strategies must adopt a holistic perspective. Integrated planning, involving collaboration between government, local communities, and the private sector, is essential. Policies should promote responsible tourism practices, balancing economic benefits with environmental and socio-cultural preservation.

The lessons drawn from Karakalpakstan's experience offer valuable insights for sustainable tourism development beyond its borders. Similar regions facing ecological fragility and rich cultural heritage can draw inspiration from the region's challenges and successes. This discussion contributes to the broader discourse on responsible tourism, emphasizing the need for context-specific strategies grounded in environmental, socio-

cultural, and economic considerations.

Moving forward, research and policy efforts should focus on implementing the identified strategies. Long-term monitoring and adaptive management are crucial for ensuring the continued sustainability of tourism in Karakalpakstan. Collaborative initiatives at the international level can facilitate knowledge exchange and contribute to a global framework for sustainable tourism practices.

In conclusion, our discussion illuminates the complexities of sustainable tourism development in Karakalpakstan and provides a foundation for informed decision-making. By addressing the ecological, socio-cultural, and economic dimensions holistically, the region can pave the way for a resilient and responsible tourism model, serving as a beacon for sustainable practices worldwide.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study has provided valuable insights into the multifaceted landscape of sustainable tourism development in Karakalpakstan. The synthesis of findings across ecological, socio-cultural, and economic dimensions illuminates the challenges and opportunities inherent in the region's tourism paradigm. Key discoveries include the delicate balance required for ecological sustainability, the significance of community engagement in socio-cultural preservation, and the economic contributions of tourism to the local economy.

The broader implications of our research extend beyond Karakalpakstan, offering lessons for regions with similar ecological fragility and cultural richness. The need for integrated strategies, considering the interconnected nature of sustainability dimensions, is evident. Our study emphasizes the importance of context-specific approaches that align with local values and engage communities actively in the tourism development process.

Looking ahead, future research in the dynamic field of sustainable tourism should delve into the effectiveness of implemented strategies in Karakalpakstan over time. Longitudinal studies can assess the adaptive capacity of the region's tourism model and provide insights into its long-term sustainability. Additionally, comparative analyses with other regions facing similar challenges can contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of global sustainable tourism practices.

As technology and global dynamics evolve, the role of digital platforms, artificial intelligence, and innovative marketing strategies in promoting sustainable tourism deserves exploration. Assessing the resilience of communities to external shocks, such as pandemics or environmental disasters, is another avenue for future research.

In summary, this study not only sheds light on the current state of sustainable tourism in Karakalpakstan but also lays the groundwork for continued research in this dynamic

field. By building on the lessons learned and proposing avenues for further investigation, we contribute to the ongoing dialogue surrounding sustainable tourism, ultimately striving for a more resilient, responsible, and inclusive tourism future.

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Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Jtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

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2024-maxsus son

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«Yashil» iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot» jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.